

plateaus and mesas. As long as the topography of the formed tableland becomes high enough to laterally expose underlying weak rocks, the tableland margins become unstable and collapse. It starts as lateral spreading and rotational landslides and later often evolve to flow-like mass movements. Many of the plateaus and mesas in the Patagonian tableland are fringed by almost continuous landslides. Some mesas are already completely consumed by landslides. This study helps to understand distribution and evolution of landslides in volcanic tablelands.

Landslides on the growing folds of the Kura fold-and-thrust belt (Azerbaijan, Georgia)

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Rising hillslopes in the active fold-and-thrust regions present new landslide-prone slopes. However, studies investigating landslides in newly formed fold-and-thrust belts are limited. In this research, we analyse landslide occurrences in the Kura fold-and-thrust belt, a geologically active region at the southern edge of the Greater Caucasus. This area has experienced significant tectonic shaping over the last 2-3 million years, affecting Miocene to Quaternary sediments. Using satellite imagery, we identified about 1600 landslides, a quarter of which are active. These landslides, although occupying less than 1% of the land, are predominantly found at higher elevations and areas with greater relief. They mainly occur in regions elevated by tectonic forces, especially on steep anticlines and valley slopes cut by active faults. Our findings lead to a conceptual model for the temporal evolution of landslide patterns in weak sediment-based fold-and-thrust belts: 1) Initially, slow deformations at thrust fronts lead to landslides in deep valleys intersecting the uplifting hanging walls. 2) As anticlines rise and steepen, they become more prone to planar sliding when dip slopes exceed friction angle, and valley development creates additional dip slopes resulting in widespread landslides. 3) Finally, erosion lowers relief, forming badlands and reducing landslide occurrence.

Geomorphometric studies of valley network in the Stołowe Mountains

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The tableland of the Stołowe Mountains, due to its distinctiveness, complexity resulting from the occurrence of sedimentary and crystalline rocks, and long research history, constitutes an excellent field for analysing relief development in tableland settings and serves as a research laboratory for testing various methods of relief parametrization. The valley network was the subject of analysis. The aim of the study was to detect and quantify similarities and differences in the fluvio-

denudational morphology of the massif. Following the concepts of connectivity and hierarchy in geomorphic systems, components of various scales were considered: catchments, basins, valleys and valley segments. Characterization of morphogenetic domains in the context of the valley network was performed. Investigation of drainage spatial pattern revealed seven classes of erosional dissection, within which various valley styles (i.e. gorges, canyons, V-shaped valleys, broad troughs and flat-bottomed valleys) in different morphological position (plateau top surface, escarpment, slope) occurred. Three main zones of enhanced erosional signal have been distinguished. Multiple track analysis shows that morphological diversity of valley systems expresses the complexity of geological setting, relief and geomorphic processes. Detailed parametrization of valley morphology of Stołowe Mountains offers a new, more quantitative look at this complex area, hidden beneath forest cover.

Anthropogenic impact on the water course in the Labe (Elbe) and Jizera confluence area

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The impact of human activities on the landscape has significantly changed throughout history. Especially, the natural evolution of rivers was extensively disrupted by course modifications and water management. Presented research evaluates the anthropogenic impact on the evolution of the middle Labe (river-km 854 –882) and the lower Jizera (river-km 0 – 17) and its influence on the dynamics of the fluvial processes. The historical change analysis of the water courses was based on the historical maps of the Second and the Third military survey, various artworks and field reconnaissance. The most significant changes of the studied sections of the Labe and Jizera course occurred during the 19th century mostly for flood protection and transport purposes. During the last 200 years, the Labe was shortened by 20.6% and the Jizera by 7.4 % of its original length. The longitudinal profiles of the Labe and Jizera were disrupted by water management structures. Recently, the lower reaches of the Jizera show a lengthening and curving tendency caused by fluvial erosion and accumulation. The reinforcements of the Labe banks limit the natural evolution of its channel. As a result of irreversible landform changes, a valuable record of their past evolution has been lost.